

Rehabilitation of Partially Edentulous Mandibular Arch With Claspless Cast Partial Denture

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A 55-year-old female patient came to the department with existing maxillary removable partial denture and Kennedy's class I modification I situation in lower arch.

Pre-OP Photographs

Occlusal view of maxillary arch and mandibular arch

Pre-operative OPG

Tooth preparation # 32,33,44

Single step putty-light body impression of mandibular arch

Intra-oral photograph of FPD with precision attachment (SAGIX)

Pick-up impression

Extra-oral photographs of Final Prosthesis

Intra-oral photographs of Final Prosthesis

**Extra-oral Post-operative
photograph**

Patient was satisfied with previous maxillary partial denture. Mandibular ridge was severely resorbed so fixed dental prosthesis (FDP) w.r.t 33-44 with bilateral precision attachment supported Cast Partial Denture was advised to enhance support and retention to the prosthesis.